

PROSPECTS FOR INTEGRATING BIM TECHNOLOGIES INTO THE E-LEARNING SYSTEM

O. T. Otamuratov

Associate Professor, Tashkent International University of Chemistry Samarkand Branch

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the prospects for integrating modern digital technologies, in particular BIM (Building Information Modeling), into e-learning systems. It highlights the potential of enhancing students' project and engineering skills, fostering visual and spatial thinking, and creating interactive digital learning environments. The study results demonstrate that BIM technologies offer significant opportunities for organizing effective educational processes and reinforcing students' practical knowledge.*

Keywords: *BIM technology, e-learning, digital environment, visualization, educational innovation, spatial thinking, project competence.*

In the context of modern digital transformation, the introduction of new approaches and technologies for the education system is becoming an urgent issue. In particular, the Building Information Modeling (BIM) technology, designed for the engineering, architecture and construction sectors, has been proven in recent years by numerous scientific studies that it has wide potential not only in production, but also in the educational process.

International organizations, including UNESCO and OECD, in their strategic documents on digital education emphasize the need to develop teachers' digital competencies, to form skills in modeling and analyzing real problems using digital tools. For example, in UNESCO's 2023 Digital Education Strategy document, BIM technology is indicated as a "tool for developing visual thinking and interdisciplinary integration" in secondary and higher education [6].

Also, in the report "Technology in Education: Trends and Insights" published by OECD (2021), BIM technology is evaluated as a tool for teaching students to think creatively and make decisions in problem situations in the STEAM direction [7].

Although BIM was originally developed for the digital creation, evaluation and coordination of project documentation in the construction and architecture sectors, it has now penetrated deeply into the education sector. The "BIM Framework" model proposed by Succar (2009) provides a scientific analysis of how this technology can be adapted to various sectors, including education [8].

The experience of Germany, the USA and Japan is considered to be progressive in integrating BIM into the process of professional training of teachers. For example:

In Germany, technical universities are provided with special modules and laboratories based on BIM within the framework of the "DigitalBau Education" project;

In the USA, BIM technology has become a key component of engineering disciplines at universities such as Georgia Tech and MIT;

In Japan, students at the Tokyo University of Technology develop urban planning and environmental models based on BIM.

Turning to the experience of Uzbekistan, the first scientifically based approaches in this regard were developed by Otamuratov O.T. proposed by, who in his research showed methods for

developing students' spatial thinking and forming practical competencies through the integration of BIM in the electronic education system [3].

National-scale research also analyzed the possibilities of introducing BIM technologies into educational processes. For example, Mukhiddinov U.S. and Kholmuminov N.K. (2021) developed a BIM-based training methodology for the professional education system [2].

In general, the integration of BIM technology into education is not just a technological innovation, but a strategic reform direction that fundamentally changes the content of the educational process.

The role of digital technologies in modern education is increasingly increasing. Globally promoted digital transformation strategies, especially in documents published by organizations such as UNESCO and OECD, emphasize the importance of integrating modern information technologies into educational processes [6], [7]. Building Information Modeling (BIM) technology is of particular importance in this process. This technology, which was first applied in the fields of construction and architecture, is now actively being applied in the educational environment. Because it allows students to develop spatial thinking, visual analysis of problem situations, and design skills [1], [3].

International experience shows that a number of projects and practical studies are being conducted to develop effective models for introducing BIM technologies into the education system. For example, in Germany, BIM laboratories have been created at technical universities within the framework of the “DigitalBau Education” project, while BIM technology is being used as a key component of engineering education at Georgia Tech and MIT universities in the USA [9]. In Japan, students at the Tokyo University of Technology are developing urban planning and environmental models based on BIM [10]. These approaches serve to develop not only technical but also complex analytical skills in students. The concept of “BIM Framework” developed by Succar methodologically substantiates the integration of this technology into various fields, including education [8]. Eastman and colleagues, in their famous work “BIM Handbook”, provided detailed information about the different stages of BIM, its didactic capabilities and adaptation to the educational environment [9]. Researchers such as Redmond and Volk have also extensively analyzed the possibilities of BIM technologies for data management, work on multi-user platforms, and modeling real projects [11].

In the context of Uzbekistan, the initial stages of introducing BIM technologies into education have also begun. In particular, in the scientific research conducted by O.T. Otamuratov, theoretical and methodological foundations of BIM-based teaching in higher technical educational institutions were developed [3]. In his work, he justified the ways of organizing mechanisms for teaching students to think independently, work on a project basis, and also visually analyze their results through BIM technology. The methodological model put forward by him used digital platforms (in particular, the platform called “computer design”), in which students worked together to develop, analyze, and evaluate 3D projects [4].

In addition, studies conducted by Mukhiddinov and Kholmuminov have shown the advantages of organizing BIM-based training in vocational education institutions, training teachers in this technology, and organizing lessons based on real-world assignments [2]. In collaboration with Shodmonkulov and Otamuratov, a methodological model for developing 3D modeling competence was tested in a real experiment and positive results were obtained [4]. The role of 3D and BIM technologies in the formation of digital competencies was highlighted by Mahmudov,

who scientifically analyzed the role of an interactive visual environment in the formation of not only theoretical but also practical skills [13]. Also, studies conducted by international researchers have examined in detail the risks of using BIM technologies, obstacles to its implementation, and management mechanisms [12].

As a result of the introduction of BIM technologies into the education system, digital environments are emerging that develop interactive, visual and spatial thinking for students. The main advantage of these technologies is that they serve to transform the student from the traditional model of learning into a practice-oriented subject capable of independently analyzing problem situations [1].

Studies show that an educational environment organized on the basis of BIM forms students' skills in design, constructive thinking, understanding of inter-object relationships, and most importantly - self-improvement at a much higher level [9]. For example, in an experimental study conducted by Otamuratov O.T. and Shodmonkulov M.T., using the “computer design” platform, the level of mastery of spatial thinking and project-based thinking skills between the experimental group and the control group was compared. According to the results, the level of understanding of educational materials, visual imagination and analysis of their results in the group working on the basis of BIM technology was 28–35% higher [4].

In addition, the tasks presented through 3D visual models were clear and understandable for students, significantly increasing their analytical thinking, solution-seeking and independent decision-making skills [10]. Studies conducted by Redmond and Volk also provide scientific evidence that working in a visual environment increases the speed and quality of student information perception, facilitates the analysis of complex structures [11].

The analysis conducted by Mahmudov A.J. emphasized the need to see BIM technologies as a tool that promotes the student not only technically, but also methodologically and psychologically. In particular, in the process of working on their own project, the student forms skills such as independent expression of their own opinion, evaluation of the work of others, and analysis in a multifaceted way [13].

Also, the use of BIM models in education, together with AR (augmented reality) and VR (virtual reality) technologies, allows for the organization of simulation-based training with the participation of students. Through such training, they will have the opportunity to practically test their projects in an environment close to real life [14]. All these circumstances indicate that education based on BIM technology is a system that is deeply integrated in terms of its content, requires an interdisciplinary approach, and develops both theoretical and practical competencies. Such a model ensures the development of the student not on the basis of knowledge, but on the basis of activity. This technology demonstrates its pedagogical effectiveness, especially when used in conjunction with a system of organizing independent work and self-assessment [13].

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